

THE ISSUE OF SPEECH DEVELOPMENT IN PRIMARY EDUCATION

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Abstract: In this article, the issue of speech development in primary education is analyzed scientifically and theoretically.

Key words: Foreign countries, attention to our language, interest in learning, era of globalization, every nation, every independent state, national interests, own culture, ancient values, mother tongue, etc.

In the process of wide-ranging reforms implemented in our country, the importance and influence of the state language in our life is increasing. The Uzbek language is actively used in the political-legal, socio-economic, spiritual-educational aspects, and is being heard on international forums. Attention and interest in studying it is increasing. In today's era of globalization, every nation, every independent state must ensure its national interests, in this regard, first of all, its culture. It is natural that priority should be given to the preservation and development of ancient values and the mother tongue." Language is the greatest national value. Language is not only a means of communication, but also a basis for innovation as a product of thinking. In addition to the function of communication in society, language also performs the functions of emotional influence and accumulation. In the process of globalization, the social function of language is expanding. Analysis of language and society, language and thinking, language and speech relations, language formation, development, history of writing, importance, emergence and development of language, description and classification of world languages, study of basic concepts of linguistics and methods of analysis, development of human society knowledge about the nature of the rich language and its use serves to form skills and competences. The science "Theory of Linguistics" provides information about the main issues of linguistics. The first part of the "Theory of Linguistics" provides an initial understanding of the formation, development, and classification of world languages, while the second part of the "General Linguistics" course focuses on the analysis of theories, doctrines, ideas, and linguistic methods in world linguistics! gan. The science "Theory of Linguistics" sheds light on the socio-economic, biological, physiological and social value of language, the development of world linguistics, the history of doctrines, the stages of theoretical views, language levels, the degree of reflection of existence in human thought and language, its diversity, the world provides information about

methods of linguistic knowledge, means of communication, processes of formation of linguistic departments. In the process of wide-ranging reforms implemented in our country, the importance and influence of the state language in our life is increasing. The Uzbek language is actively used in the political-legal, socio-economic, spiritual-educational aspects, and is being heard on international forums. attention and interest in studying it is increasing. In today's era of globalization, every nation, every independent state must ensure its national interests, in this regard, first of all, its culture. It is natural that priority should be given to the preservation and development of ancient values and the mother tongue." Language is the greatest national value. Language is not only a means of communication, but also a basis for innovation as a product of thinking. In addition to the function of communication in society, language also performs the functions of emotional influence and accumulation. In the process of globalization, the social function of language is expanding. Analysis of language and society, language and thinking, language and speech relations, language formation, development, history of writing, importance, emergence and development of language, description and classification of world languages, study of basic concepts of linguistics and methods of analysis, development of human society knowledge about the nature of the rich language and its use serves to form skills and competences. The science "Theory of Linguistics" provides information about the main issues of linguistics. The first part of the "Theory of Linguistics" provides an initial understanding of the formation, development, and classification of world languages, while the second part of the "General Linguistics" course focuses on the analysis of theories, doctrines, ideas, and linguistic methods in world linguistics! gan. The science "Theory of Linguistics" sheds light on the socio-economic, biological, physiological and social value of language, the development of world linguistics, the history of doctrines, the stages of theoretical views, language levels, the degree of reflection of existence in human thought and language, its diversity, the world provides information about methods of linguistic knowledge, means of communication, processes of formation of linguistic departments. The result of this was the emergence of "new" linguistics in our country (speech linguistics, psycho-, social-, pragmatic, text linguistics, etc.), the revival of classical rhetoric, the formation of neo-rhetoric based on it, its practical field. humanitarian knowledge designed to influence the development of communication skills of a person. Currently, ontolinguistics occupies a huge scientific space in science, it studies the ontogenesis of speech, the process of developing communication

tools in a child. Knowledge of laws The development of human speech is not only theoretical, but, I would say, of national importance. Every parent, teacher, school teacher, psychologist, speech therapist, coach, university lecturer, doctor, etc. It is necessary (I emphasize this word) to know how to develop the ability to communicate with a child, teenager, young man. How does this process relate to the development of the intelligence of the developing individual? What is the role of people surrounding the child? They need to know what contributes to and encourages its normal, full course, and what can interfere with the evolution of speech, disrupt it. This knowledge can save a little person from big problems in his future life. They can help all of us to raise a healthy, well-rounded generation, the generation of future citizens of our country. In addition, ontopsy-Holinguistics performs a task familiar to the humanities: it allows to build a bridge between people of different ages and help society solve the eternal problem of fathers and children. In our country, there are scientific centers that are tasked with the scientific and civilian study of the little-known laws of the development of the speech and thinking of a person who is literally developing before our eyes, and the search for mechanisms of influence on it started His linguistic personality appeared everywhere in Russia: in Moscow, Saratov, Samara, Voronezh, Orel, Taganrog, Kemerovo, Tomsk, Vladivostok and other cities. The largest school of ontolinguistics appeared in St. Petersburg (Leningrad at that time), and as a "scientific Mecca" the head of the newly established "Children's speech" department, Professor S.N. Zeitlin. Thanks to the efforts of S. N. Tseitlin at the Russian State Pedagogical University. A.I. Hertsen (I repeat) created a unique department of children's speech, in which a workshop on ontological speech problems has been working for twenty years. genesis of linguistic consciousness. Within the framework of the seminar, preliminary defenses of candidacy and doctoral dissertations, meetings, conferences and symposia are held, and many collections of scientific articles, monographs, and training manuals are published. The atmosphere of tolerance and interest in different points of view, in which the author of these lines is a constant participant, which always prevails in these scientific meetings, allowed the department to strengthen the achievements of scientists of various fields of linguistics and other disciplines. In conclusion, it should be noted that modern methods of speech development in children are effective and important.

References:

1. Hayitov H. A. Sharq mumtoz adabiyotida ohang talqini //Мировая наука. – 2019. – №. 8. – С. 3-5.

2. Ahmadovich H. H., Amrulloeyevna S. D. XX ASR QISSACHILIGI TARAQQIYOTIDA FOLKLORNING LATIFA JANRI TA'SIRI //PEDAGOGS jurnali. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 1. – C. 302-304.
3. Ahmadovich H. H. Expression of Folklorisms in the Works of Ghafur Ghulam //European Journal of Life Safety and Stability (2660-9630). – 2022. – T. 14. – C. 101-105.
4. Ahmadovich H. H. et al. BOSHLANG 'ICH SINFLARDA O 'ZBEK QISSALARI TAHLILINING INNOVATSION USULLARI //PEDAGOGS jurnali. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 1. – C. 350-352.
5. Ahmadovich H. H. et al. O 'RXUN-YENISEY BITIKLARIDA TALIM-TARBIYA TO 'G 'RISIDAGI FIKRLARNING YORITILISHI VA ULARNING TARBIYAVIY AHAMIYATI //PEDAGOGS jurnali. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 1. – C. 349-350.
6. Ahmadovich H. H. et al. IJODIY TOPSHIRIQLAR O 'QUV MOTIVLARINI SHAKLLANTIRISHNING SAMARALI VOSITASI SIFATIDA //PEDAGOGS jurnali. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 1. – C. 293-294.
7. Ahmadovich H. H. et al. BOSHLANG 'ICH TA'LIMDA O 'ZLASHTIRISH JARAYONINING PSIXO-DIDAKTIK ASOSLARI //PEDAGOGS jurnali. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 1. – C. 332-334.
8. Ahmadovich H. H. et al. O 'QUVCHILARNING BILUV FAOLLIGINI OSHIRISHGA QARATILGAN DARSDAN TASHQARI ISHLAR VA ULARNI TASHKIL ETISH METODIKASI //PEDAGOGS jurnali. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 1. – C. 343-345.
9. Ahtamovich H. H., Shixnazarovna J. A. O 'QUVCHILAR O 'ZLASHTIRISH DARAJALARINI TASHHISLASH //PEDAGOGS jurnali. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 1. – C. 306-309.
10. Ahmadovich H. H., Aminovna A. S. BOSHLANG 'ICH SINF O 'QISH DARSLARIDA DIDAKTIK O 'YIN VA INTERFAOL USULLARDAN FOYDALANISH //PEDAGOGS jurnali. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 1. – C. 100-102.
11. Ahmadovich H. H., Amrulloeyevna S. D. RUNN BITIKLARI AXLOQ VA VATANPARVARLIKNING YUKSAK NAMUNASI SIFATIDA //PEDAGOGS jurnali. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 1. – C. 248-250.
12. Ahmadovich K. H., Bahriddinovna S. G. Development and practical application of acmeological technologies of student assessment diagnose //Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research. – 2022. – T. 11. – №. 6. – C. 141-145.
13. Ahmadovich K. H., ZokirovnaZ A. G. THE PROBLEM OF HUMAN EDUCATION AND MORALITY IN FOLKLORE //Gospodarka i Innowacje. – 2022. – T. 25. – C. 133-137.

14. Ahmadovich K. H., Nodirkulovna A. I. Theory of Fairy Tales in Primary Grades, The Nature of the Fairy Tale Genre //American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 7. – С. 130-133.
15. BuxDUPI H. A. H. et al. AKMEOLOGIYA VA UNING O'QUVCHILAR O'ZLASHTIRISHINI TASHXISLASHDAGI O'RNI //PEDAGOGS jurnali. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 415-417.
16. Хаитов Х. Адабиётда кулгидан фойдаланиш анъанасининг асослари //Общество и инновации. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 3/С. – С. 49-52.
17. Ҳайитов Ҳ. А. ЛЎЛИ НОМИ БИЛАН БОҒЛИҚ ЛАТИФАЛАРНИНГ ЎЗИГА ХОС ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ //Интернаука. – 2021. – №. 17-4. – С. 51-52.
18. Hayitov H. A. QUSHLARGA IBRAT-HAZRATI XIZR! //Интернаука. – 2020. – №. 12-3. – С. 72-73.
19. Khoja o'g'li T., Ahmadovich K. H. Advanced Characteristics of the Tradition of Using Uzbek Folk Humor Art in Written Literature //American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 9. – С. 1-4.
20. Khaitov H., Amonova S. ЎЗБЕК ҲИКОЯ ВА ҚИССАЛАРИДА КУЛГИ МАДАНИЯТИНИНГ ИЛДИЗЛАРИ //Journal of Integrated Education and Research. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 2. – С. 140-144.
21. Ahtamovich H. H., Shixnazarovna J. A. O 'QUVCHILAR O 'ZLASHTIRISH DARAJALARINI TASHHISLASH //PEDAGOGS jurnali. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 306-309.
22. Akhmadovich X. X. et al. ENG QADIMGI MA'RIFIY YODGORLIKLARNI O 'RGANISHNING AHAMIYATI //PEDAGOGS jurnali. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 281-285.
23. Ҳайитов Х. А. ҒАФУР ҒУЛОМНИНГ ХАЛҚ ЛАТИФАЛАРИДАН ФОЙДАЛАНИШ МАҲОРАТИ //Academic research in educational sciences. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 3. – С. 679-687.
24. Akhmadovich H. H. Khoja nasriddin afandi as people's hero //ACADEMICIA: AN INTERNATIONAL MULTIDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH JOURNAL. – 2021. – Т. 11. – №. 2. – С. 1562-1565.
25. Akhmadovich K. K. Symbolism of Birds in Uzbek Literature //International Journal on Integrated Education. – Т. 3. – №. 4. – С. 59-63.
26. Hayitov H. A. Literary influence and artistic image //Экономика и социум. – 2019. – №. 8. – С. 11-14.

